

VARIATIONS IN THE STOCHASTIC BEHAVIOR OF PARTIAL-DISCHARGE PULSES WITH POINT-TO-DIELECTRIC GAP SPACING

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ABSTRACT

The stochastic behavior of ac-generated partial-discharge pulses in a point-to-dielectric air gap has been thoroughly characterized from direct measurements of various conditional and unconditional phase-restricted pulse-height and phase-of-occurrence distributions. The results reveal significant pulse-to-pulse and phase-to-phase memory propagation at all gap spacings. The observed memory effects are seen to be important in controlling the initiation and growth probabilities of partial-discharge pulses at any given phase of the applied voltage.

INTRODUCTION

The use of phase-resolved partial-discharge (PD) patterns for identification of defects in electrical insulation has been considered for many years [1,2]. Efforts are now underway to statistically quantify PD patterns using computer assisted measurement and analysis technique [3-6]. Progress in the development of reliable automated methods for PD pattern recognition has been hampered by a failure to understand the physical mechanisms that determine the stochastic properties of PD phenomena.

It has been shown by recent research [7-9] that PD's can exhibit complex stochastic behavior in which memory effects play an important role. Memory results from the influence of residuals such as surface charge or ion space charge produced by earlier discharge events on the initiation and growth of subsequent discharges. A complete physical description of PD phenomena must necessarily include the effects of memory propagation. It cannot be assumed that these effects are negligible.

Using a recently developed real-time stochastic analyzer, it is possible to measure sets of conditional pulse-amplitude distributions that provide a quantification of memory effects, e.g., it is possible to determine the dependences of the discharge initiation probabilities at particular phases of the applied voltage on the amplitudes and/or phases-of-occurrence of prior PD events. It has already been shown [8,9] that in a point-dielectric gap, the most probable phases-of-occurrence of PD pulses in one half-cycle are dependent on the magnitude of discharge events that occurred in the previous half-cycle. Measurable memory effects can, in fact, propagate back beyond the most recent half-cycle.

A stochastic analyzer was used in the present investigation to examine changes in the stochastic behavior of PD pulses that occur when the gap distance between a point electrode and a solid planar dielectric surface is varied.

MEASUREMENT METHOD

The measurements were performed with an expanded version of U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. copyright.

a unique real-time stochastic analyzer previously used to investigate the stochastic properties of pulsating dc corona discharges [7,10,11]. The present instrument includes an option for measurement of ac phase-correlated, or phase-restricted unconditional or conditional PD amplitude and phase-of-occurrence distributions [12]. Examples of measurable conditional distributions for which results are presented here include: $p_1(\phi_i^\pm | Q^\mp)$; $p_1(q_i^\pm | \phi_i^\pm)$; $p_1(q_i^\pm | \Delta\phi_{i,i-1}^\pm = \phi_i^\pm - \phi_{i-1}^\pm)$; $p_2(\phi_i^\pm | q_{i-1}^\pm, \phi_{i-1}^\pm)$; $p_2(q_i^\pm | Q^\mp, \phi_i^\pm)$, where the notation is consistent with Figure 1, e.g., ϕ_i^\pm and q_i^\pm are respectively the phase and amplitude of the *i*th pulse to appear on the positive half-cycle. Here Q^+ (or Q^-) denotes the net charge associated with PD pulses on the previous positive (or negative) half-cycle, i.e.,

$$Q^\pm = \sum_i q_i^\pm \quad (1)$$

The conditional distributions are defined such that, for example, $p_2(q_i^+ | Q^-, \phi_i^+) dq_i^+$ is the probability that the *i*th pulse in the

Figure 1 - Diagrammatic representation of the partial-discharge pulses for different point-to-dielectric gap spacings. Indicated is the sinusoidal gap voltage, $V_a(t)$, and the amplitudes and phases of individual PD events.

positive half-cycle will have an amplitude in the range q_i^+ to $q_i^+ + dq_i^+$ if it occurs at a fixed phase, ϕ_i^+ , and if the total charge associated with all PD pulses in the previous negative half-cycle has a fixed value Q^- . In the actual measurement process, the "fixed" variables lie within specified restricted ranges.

The "positive" and "negative" half-cycles refer specifically to the respective phase regions where positive and negative PD pulses appear. These phase regions can lag the phases of the applied voltage $V_a(t)$ because of shifts in the local electric-field strength due to charging of the dielectric surface by PD activity. These shifts can result in PD pulses appearing before the voltage zero crossing [9].

The discharge pulses were produced with a point-planar dielectric gap in room air similar to that used for a previous investigation of dc corona pulses [11]. The stainless-steel point electrode with a tip radius-of-curvature of about 0.05 mm could be positioned along an axis perpendicular to and centered on a 4×8 cm rectangular solid dielectric surface. The gap spacing, d , could be varied from 0 to 10 cm. The dielectric was either a flat, 1 mm thick polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) or cast epoxy insulator that was directly fastened to a metal surface. All data reported here were obtained with a 200 Hz, 3.0 kV rms sinusoidal voltage applied to the gap.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Similar results were obtained for both types of dielectric surfaces although the epoxy appeared to "age" more quickly than PTFE when exposed to the discharge. As a consequence of the aging process, presumably due to discharge-induced modifications of the surface, it was found that the PD generated using epoxy were more susceptible to nonstationary behavior as expected [12], thus making it more difficult to perform "complete" characterizations of the PD stochastics under ostensibly identical conditions. Therefore, except where specifically indicated, the results reported here apply only to the PTFE dielectric.

Figure 2 shows plots of the mean number of measured positive PD pulses, $\langle n^+ \rangle$, and maximum number of negative PD pulses, n_{\max}^- , per cycle versus gap spacing. For both dielectrics, it is seen that positive pulses appear at a rate of one or more per cycle only for $d < 1.0$ cm; whereas negative pulses appear even at $d = 6.0$ cm. At gap spacings greater than 1.0 cm, where positive discharge pulses are absent, the negative discharge exhibits the characteristics of regular self-sustained Trichel pulses [7,11] that are nearly symmetrically distributed about $\phi = 3\pi/2$ (see Figure 1). This characteristic is well known from earlier work [2].

The number of Trichel pulses per negative half-cycle increases with decreasing gap spacing and reaches a slight maximum at $d \approx 2.0$ cm. Below 2.0 cm, the negative-corona pulse rate decreases consistent with the effect previously noted for dc discharges [11] which is due to a reduction in electric-field strength at the point electrode produced by charge deposited on the dielectric surface by the corona. When the positive pulses appear at $d \approx 1.0$ cm, the negative pulse rate again increases with decreasing distance. This is expected due to positive discharges neutralizing the surface charge deposited during the negative corona. For gap spacings in the range $1.0 \text{ cm} > d > 0.0$ cm, the Trichel pulses become more random in both phase and amplitude as illustrated in Figure 1 for $d = 0.15$ cm. When the point electrode "touches" the dielectric surface, the negative discharge pulse rate drops precipitously and, as discussed below, the stochastic behavior ceases to be that characteristic of Trichel pulses.

Figure 2 - Maximum number of negative PD pulses, n_{\max}^- , and mean number of positive PD pulses, $\langle n^+ \rangle$ versus gap distance for epoxy and PTFE dielectrics.

Figure 3 shows plots of the measured phase-of-occurrence distributions for the first and last negative-corona pulses, i.e., $p_o(\phi_i^-)$ for $i = 1$ and n_{\max}^- respectively, at different gap spacings together with the corresponding mean phase values (dashed lines) computed from $p_o(\phi_i^-)$ using

$$\langle \phi_i^- \rangle = \int_0^{2\pi} p_o(\phi_i^-) \phi_i^- d\phi_i^- . \quad (2)$$

Also displayed in this figure is the same plot of n_{\max}^- versus d shown in Figure 2 for PTFE and the centroid for all negative pulses (dot-dashed line). An expansion of the region below 1.5 cm where positive pulses occur is shown in Figure 4. In this figure,

Figure 3 - Measured phase-of-occurrence distributions, $p_o(\phi_i^-)$, and corresponding mean values, $\langle \phi_i^- \rangle$, for the first ($i = 1$) and last ($i = n_{\max}^-$) negative PD pulses versus gap distance for PTFE. Also shown is the same plot of n_{\max}^- versus d given in Figure 2 and the spacing below which positive pulses occur.

Figure 4 - Measured phase-of-occurrence distributions of the first negative PD pulse and unconditional amplitude distributions of the corresponding positive PD pulses versus gap distance for PTFE. Also indicated by the dashed lines are the corresponding mean values $\langle \phi_1^- \rangle$ and $\langle q_i^+, i \geq 1 \rangle$.

$p_o(\phi_1^-)$ and $\langle \phi_1^- \rangle$ are compared with the corresponding unconditional positive-pulse amplitude distributions and mean values, i.e., $p_o(q_i^+, i \geq 1)$ and $\langle q_i^+, i \geq 1 \rangle$ respectively. It is seen in Figures 3 that the centroid of negative pulses shifts toward the zero crossing, $\phi/\pi = 1.0$, at gap spacings where the positive pulses appear. The magnitude of the shift tends to increase for increasing amplitude of the positive pulses. Under some conditions the first pulse in the “negative half-cycle” may actually occur with finite probability before the voltage zero crossing, i.e., for $\phi_1^-/\pi < 1.0$.

The results in Figures 3 and 4 suggest the existence of phase-to-phase memory effects, e.g., the occurrence of PD pulses in the positive half-cycle influences the initiation and development of PD pulses in the subsequent negative half-cycle. The existence of memory propagation is unequivocally verified by the data for the conditional phase and amplitude distributions $p_1(\phi_1^-|Q^+)$ and $p_2(q_1^-|\phi_1^-, Q^+)$ of the first negative pulse shown in Figure 5. This figure displays data for the successively higher order conditional amplitude distributions and, in the lower right corner, the corresponding conditional and unconditional phase-of-occurrence distributions at $d \simeq 1.2$ mm. The distributions in Figure 5 are related by the integral expressions [7,9]

$$p_o(q_1^-) = \int_0^{2\pi} p_o(\phi_1^-) p_1(q_1^-|\phi_1^-) d\phi_1^- \quad (3)$$

$$p_o(\phi_1^-) = \int_0^\infty p_o(Q^+) p_1(\phi_1^-|Q^+) dQ^+ \quad (4)$$

$$p_1(q_1^-|\phi_1^-) = \int_0^\infty p_o(Q^+) p_1(\phi_1^-|Q^+) p_2(q_1^-|\phi_1^-, Q^+) dQ^+ \quad (5)$$

Note that the integrated positive charge distribution, $p_o(Q^+)$, is needed to complete the analysis. This distribution was also measured, but is not shown here.

Consistent with a simple model for a dielectric-barrier type PD process [8,9], the results in Figure 5 indicate that as Q^+ increases the mean phase-of-occurrence, $\langle \phi_1^- (Q^+) \rangle$, of the first pulse on the next half-cycle decreases; and for a fixed phase, ϕ_1^- , $\langle q_1^- (Q^+, \phi_1^-) \rangle$ increases. The relevant expectation values are given by

$$\langle \phi_1^- (Q^+) \rangle = \int_0^{2\pi} \phi_1^- p_1(\phi_1^-|Q^+) d\phi_1^-, \quad (6)$$

$$\langle q_1^- (Q^+, \phi_1^-) \rangle = \int_0^\infty q_1^- p_2(q_1^-|Q^+, \phi_1^-) dq_1^-. \quad (7)$$

Figure 6 shows examples of data obtained at $d \simeq 1.5$ mm for $p_1(\phi_1^-|Q^+ \pm \delta Q^+)$ that demonstrate a dependence of $\langle \phi_1^- (Q^+) \rangle$ on Q^+ even for $i > 1$.

In addition to the influence that PD events on one half-cycle can have on PD behavior in subsequent half-cycles, there can also be significant memory propagation from one event to the next within a given half-cycle. This is demonstrated by the data shown in Figures 7 and 8. Figure 7 shows measured second-order conditional phase-of-occurrence distributions $p_2(\phi_3^+|\phi_2^+, q_2^+)$ for the third pulse in the positive half-cycle in comparison with the corresponding first-order distribution $p_1(\phi_3^+|\phi_2^+)$ (dashed line). The data are consistent with a simple model that predicts an increase in $\langle \phi_i^\pm (q_{i-1}^\pm, \phi_{i-1}^\pm) \rangle$ as q_{i-1}^\pm increases since the local electric-field strength reduction at the point electrode should increase with increasing amplitude of the preceding discharge pulse.

The examples of data on the conditional amplitude distributions $p_1(q_i^-|\Delta\phi_{i-1}^- = \phi_i^- - \phi_{i-1}^-)$ shown in Figure 8 for $d \simeq 1.5$ mm and $d=0.0$ mm also provide a measure of memory propagation between successive events within a half-cycle. The dependence

Figure 5 - Measured conditional and unconditional amplitude distributions of the first negative PD pulse at the indicated values of ϕ_1^- and Q^+ for PTFE and $d = 1.2$ mm. Also shown are the conditional and unconditional phase-of-occurrence distributions for the same pulse. All distributions have been arbitrarily normalized to the maximum values.

Figure 6 - Normalized conditional and corresponding unconditional phase-of-occurrence distributions of the first, eighth, and sixteenth PD pulses to appear in the negative half-cycle for PTFE and $d = 1.5$ mm.

Figure 7 - Normalized conditional distributions for the phase-of-occurrence of the third pulse in the positive half-cycle conditioned on the indicated phase and amplitude ranges for the second pulse.

of $\langle q_i^-(\Delta\phi_{i,i-1}^-) \rangle$ on the phase (or time) separation from the previous pulse at $d = 1.5$ mm is consistent with that previously reported for Trichel pulses [7,11] and can be attributed to the influence of moving negative-ion space charge on the electric-field strength at the point electrode. When $d = 0.0$ mm, the discharge must occur along or close to the dielectric surface where it is not likely to be affected by negative ions generated during previous discharge events. It is seen from the data in Figure 8 that in

Figure 8 - Measured conditional amplitude distributions and corresponding mean amplitude values measured for PTFE at the indicated gap spacings. All distributions are normalized the maximum values.

this case $\langle q_i^-(\Delta\phi_{i,i-1}^-) \rangle$ exhibits much less dependence on $\Delta\phi_{i,i-1}^-$ than occurs for Trichel pulses. The increased broadening of the conditional distributions with increasing phase difference evident in some cases at $d = 0.0$ mm remains unexplained, but may be related to the dynamics of surface charging and surface charge migration that occurs during and after a PD event.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown how it is possible, by direct measurement of conditional PD pulse-amplitude and phase-of-occurrence distributions, to obtain detailed information about the stochastic properties of PD pulses needed to unravel effects of memory propagation. The data presented clearly reveal that partial discharges generated by applying an alternating voltage to a point-dielectric discharge gap have a complex stochastic behavior that is sensitively dependent on gap spacing. The importance of phase-to-phase and pulse-to-pulse memory propagation in controlling the probabilities for discharge initiation and growth has been established.

At large gap spacings ($d > 1.0$ cm), discharge pulses occur only on the negative half-cycle and the pulse-to-pulse memory effects are predominantly due to negative-ion space charge and metastable excited species which has been shown in previous work on Trichel pulses [7]. At small gap spacings, discharges occur on both half-cycles. The pulse-to-pulse memory propagation due to residual space charge and metastable species is augmented at these spacings by memory associated with deposition of charge on the dielectric surface during successive PD events. Because of the expected slow rate for surface-charge dissipation, this latter mechanism causes significant memory propagation between successive half-cycles of the applied voltage. At zero gap spacing, the observed stochastic behavior of the PD pulses changes dramatically due to the predominant influence of surface charging.

To a large extent, the memory effects described here account for the difficulties encountered in the interpretation of the uncon-

ditional amplitude or phase distributions determined from more traditional PD measurement methods. Moreover, these effects need to be considered in developing physical models of PD processes, i.e., the model must predict conditional distributions such as reported in this work.

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